

A Design Evaluation Method based on Emotional Reactions and Buying Intentions

A Case Study: a Lifting Storage System Designed for Small-space Residents

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Abstract: This research revealed a design evaluation method to evaluate a design before it is launched. The study was based on the design of a lifting storage system designed for small-space residents. This method involves evaluating user's emotional reactions and buying intentions. The results show that when people respond to questionnaires designed to gauge emotional reactions or buying intentions their true preferences for a particular design cannot be entirely represented; instead, their responses are highly related to individual differences; such as culture, ethnicity, preference, and personality. In addition, the presented reality-levels of a design representation and its environment also influence customer's emotional reactions, and then affect their buying decision making. A presentation dissonance (a reality conflict between a product and its environment) can result in negative emotional reactions and should be avoided.

Key words: *Design Evaluation, Emotional Reaction, Buying Intention, Culture and Design, Presentation Dissonance.*

1. Introduction

In the market place, a product can be evaluated by customers based on its aesthetics, quality, functions, and usability. However, there are more features besides those physical attributes that make a buying action happen. For instance, customers' emotional reactions to a product are essential for the success of a product. In Hansen's 2005 article, he said, "Consumers do not make their purchasing decisions independently on either cognitive (perceived quality, price, developed attitude) or affective skills (emotional reactions) [1.]" In other words, both affective and cognitive skills influence the perceived value of a product when customers make a purchasing action.

In fact, both of these skills are influenced by the attributes of a product and, most of all, the individual differences of customers; e.g. culture difference, education, personality, ethnicity, gender and etc. Regarding cultural differences, eastern collectivists tend to hide their emotional feelings when they are in public. The differences of individual and groups are blurred. Conversely, western individualists tend to present their independence and true feelings. The differences of individual and groups are clear [2.] Seeing each customer as a unique individual with personal differences can help researchers/designers evaluate the interview data accordingly.

Nevertheless, the perceived value of a product can be benefited by a proper presentation of a product in an appropriate environment; e.g. people would be more likely to buy a cup of coffee in a Starbucks because the purchasing experience is more pleasant than drinking at a bus station. As a result, the presentation of design and its environment in this study was carefully designed by the researcher/designer in order to better emotionally connect the participants to the design.

Therefore, the researcher/designer conducted a study using a comprehensive design evaluation method. Cultural differences and presentation conflicts were found through participants' responses on emotional reactions and buying intentions. Moreover, user involvement in pre production evaluation of design concepts is valuable and can save time, money, and reduce risk of failure when introduced to the market place.

2. Evaluation Interview Method

This research is based on a study involving the evaluation of a home interior lifting storage system. The system was developed based on small-space resident's needs identified in previous research. Previously, it was found that the lack of storage is the most significant complaint about their living spaces. There was an expressed desire for a product that provides extra storage space. The psychology literature (Sommer, 1974; Freedman, 1975; Kopec, 2006) tells us that many urban residents feel stressed and depressed about living in small spaces [3][4][5.] With awareness of these strong emotional reactions present, the storage system was developed by the researcher/designer based on two principles: 1.create extra storage space in a constrained space, and 2. help people live more happier and comfortably in a small space.

Figure 1. Reactions of a User to a Product and its Environment

Accordingly, the reactions of a user to a product and its environment, which are emotional feelings and surrounding stimuli (Figure 1,) should be considered and evaluated. Two sets of questionnaires were employed in order to discover the buyer's emotional feelings – an emotional reactions questionnaire and buying intentions questionnaire. There are a total of 14 kinds of emotions listed on the emotional reactions questionnaire; e.g. serenity, interest, relaxation, excitement, happiness, agitation, anger, sadness, tired, like, pleasantness, activation, stress, and pain. The participants were asked to rate on a scale of one to five on each emotion status. On the other hand, the buying intention questionnaire composed with a scale of one to ten for the designs featuring preferences (appearance, lifting, and storage capability) and overall reactions. Open questions such as money amounts willing to spend on the designs and reasons they like/dislike the designs, were included as well.

In addition, the participants were asked to report their reactions on the questionnaires (mentioned above) based on the experiences of viewing two designs, developed by the researcher, in a 3D virtual environment (Figure 2.) This was a real-time 3D interactive virtual interview tool developed by the researcher in order to simulate real

stimuli experienced in the 3D virtual space. The participants were asked to experience the designs in a designated sequence, then fill out the questionnaires.

2.1. 3D Interactive Interview Tool

As discussed above, to better visualize the designs, 3D models of three small rooms and two designs were built by the researcher/designer. The models were used to construct a virtual small-space environment for users to evaluate the designs. The three room models, duplicated from the same room model, were exactly the same size and configuration with the exception of designs 1 and 2 in rooms 2 and 3. The two design models, Design 1 and Design 2, have the same functions but with different scale. Design 1 is a small version which has three drawers underneath an open cabinet (2”D x 4” W x 2”H), and Design 2 is a wider version with ten drawers underneath an open cabinet (2”D x 10”W x 2”H). Both of them may be controlled to lift up and down by an electronic motor mounted to a ceiling. Figure 2 depicts the interface used by the participant to navigate the virtual space and the room without Design 1 or 2. Design 1 and 2 not shown because of intellectual property rights and the need to restrict public disclosure.

In order to better create the atmosphere of a small room, the configuration of the virtual room was designed with sensitivity of the participant’s perceptions. The furniture was imported from the digital resource in the book, *Introducing to Maya 2008* [6.] There was an attempt to place the furniture naturally (e.g. the books in the book shelf were tilted, the pillows on the couch were flat). The purpose of doing this was to closely connect subjects’ personal experiences to this virtual environment.

Figure 2. The Menu of Interview Tool and Room 1

In addition, the interactive interface of this interview tool was designed based on the core of user experience. Subjects quickly taught to navigate the room freely. This interview tool allows the subjects to move, look around, adjust view height depending on their height, switch between sitting or standing height, control the height of the designs, and exit the interview (Figure 3.)

Figure 3. Control Menu for Navigating the Rooms

2.2. Evaluation Interview Process

Figure 4 shows the implementation process of the evaluation interview. Ten subjects were asked to sequentially review three rooms (Room 1 with no design, Room 2 with Design 1, and Room 3 with Design 2) in less than 10 minutes per room. Their emotional reactions were monitored before and after the room exploration by using the emotional reaction questionnaire. In addition, after the exploration of Room 2 and Room 3, where two designs were presented, subjects filled out another questionnaire about buying intentions. The room without any design model was set to be a baseline room, which was a required setting in order to understand the participants' initial emotional status (Figure 2.)

Ten subjects interviewed ages 24 to 35 who live in small spaces that range 200 to 500 square feet per person. A few of the subjects have experienced living both in crowded cities in Asia and in less crowded cities in the US. Beyond the standard interview process, they were encouraged to describe issues, based on their experience, of living in these different situations.

Figure 4. Evaluation Interview Process

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Buying Intention

Based on the responses of two questionnaires, the participants, who are all small-space residents, liked the designs presented to them in the study and rated them with a high average-score—7.9 out of 10 points for Design 1, and 7.1 for Design 2 (Table 1. and Table 2.) The overall buying intentions for both designs are relatively high, 7.4 for Design 1 and 7.3 for Design 2. The features which the participants liked most were the storage capability and the appearance of the designs.

Table 1. The Buying Intentions for Design 1

Table 2. The Buying Intentions for Design 2

Interestingly, the preferences for the designs are different based on the subjects' ethnicity. As shown in both Table 3 and Figure 5, the Asian subjects liked Design 2 more than Design 1 (p value =.00110.) Their average buying intention for Design 2 is 8 points, and 6.4 points for Design 1); On the other hand, the non-Asian subjects like Design 1 more than Design 2 (p value =.00110.) Their average buying intention for Design 1 is 8.4, and only 6.6 for Design 2.

Table 3. Ethnicity and the Buying Intentions for both Designs 1 and Design 2

Figure 5. Buying Intentions for Design 1 & 2 Versus Ethnicity Group

(Group1: Asian, N=5; Group 2: Non-Asian, N=5)

The left figure shows the non-Asian subjects reported higher buying intentions for Design 1. The right figure shows the Asian subjects reported higher buying intentions for Design 2

Similarly, the money that the subjects are willing to spend on the designs also varied based on the ethnicity and their preferences (Table 4.) The participants indicated that, on average, they would be willing to spend \$250 for Design 1 and \$450 for Design 2. The subjects are willing to spend more money on the designs when they rated higher buying intentions on them. The Asian subjects are willing to spend \$401 on Design 2 which is twenty-four percent higher than the average; whereas the non-Asian subjects are willing to spend \$317 on Design 1 which is ten percent higher than the average.

Table 4. Ethnicity and the Money They are willing to Spend on the Designs

In summary, the participants, who are all small-space residents, like the designs and gave them relatively high scores: 7.9 for Design 1 and 7.1 for Design 2. This positive reaction to the designs is highly related to their buying intentions and the money they are willing to spend on the designs. Interestingly, the result also showed

the preference difference based on the subjects' ethnicity. The Asian subjects reported more interests in Design 2, whereas the non-Asian subjects showed more interests in Design 1.

3.2 Emotions

The results of the emotional reactions questionnaire were supposed to reveal the participants' feelings about using the designs in small spaces. However, they didn't show any change in their emotional status while participating in our research. There were no statistically significant results showing that the participants felt more positive or negative emotions after interacting with the designs in the virtual living room because the number of the participants were limited (N=10.) In other words, there was no direct evidence showing that the users feel happier and comfortable when using the designs in their small spaces. However, the designs did not appear to depress the users or cause any negative effects either.

The order of viewing the designs influenced the pleasant emotions the participants reported to feel. The participants who saw Design 2 before Design 1 reported more pleasant emotions than the participants who viewed the designs in the opposite orders (Figure 6. and Figure 7.) This can be explained as the Design 2 is a larger version of the lifting storage system, and the participant can directly see the benefits of using it while they first viewed it in the virtual room. As soon as they can see the benefits of the system, they naturally transferred their positive feelings to the next similar design (Design 1.) Similarly, the opposite viewing order creates the same feeling transferring but on the negative emotions (less pleasant.) In addition, more about how the presentations of a design and its environment influence users' buying intentions and emotional reactions will be discussed in section 3.3.2.

Figure 6. Pleasant Emotions Versus Viewing Orders

Conclusion

There is a statistically significant difference between point c and C. It also means the subjects who saw the Design 2 before the Design 1 reported more pleasantness comparing to the subjects who saw the designs in opposite orders.

Figure 7. Pleasant Emotions Versus Viewing Orders – Conclusion

3.3 Emotions and Buying Intentions

The participants’ emotions were assumed to have positive relations to their buying intentions [7][8.] For Design 2, the participants’ buying intentions were related to certain positive and negative emotions. The positive emotions included interest and like. The negative emotions were agitation, anger, and sadness. For example, the participants reported higher buying intentions for Design 2 while indicating higher interests and like emotions to it. Interestingly, on the other hand, the participants also reported higher buying intentions for Design 2 while indicating higher agitation, anger, and sadness emotions associated with it. Conversely, for Design 1, there were no similar findings that showed the relation between emotions and buying intentions. This finding prompted more studies on the potential factors that could influence how people emotionally react to a product and report their feelings on a questionnaire. The principle is to look at each of our customers as a unique individual with personal differences. In this research, three of the main factors that are highly related to emotional reactions and buying intentions are attitude, behavioral change, and culture difference.

3.3.1 Emotion Reactions and Buying Intentions Versus Attitude, Behavioral Changes, and Culture

Emotional reactions, buying intentions, and the actual amount that people reported they are willing to spend were inconsistent based on their ethnicity. In this study, the Asian subjects’ buying intentions were only related to their positive emotions. The non-Asian subject’s negative emotions showed highly relations to the amount of money they reported to pay for the designs. These negative emotions included agitation, anger, sadness, stress, and pain. For example, when the participant reported higher anger levels they tended to report a willingness to pay a higher price for a design.

The inconsistency of the non-Asian subjects’ attitude (emotional status) and their behaviors (buying intention, like money willing to spend) can be explained as cognitive dissonance. Leon Festinger, a psychologist, proposed this idea. Cognitive dissonance is present when people feel uncomfortable when their attitudes and behaviors are inconsistent [9][10.] People may change attitudes to match behaviors in order to relieve the cognitive dissonance (Cialdini et al, 1995.) Some researchers have also proposed that the cognitive dissonance can influence people differently based on their cultures [11][12.] In addition, for Western culture, individuals tend to exhibit behavior based on internal attitudes in different situations. They are more likely to align attitudes and behaviors. For

Eastern culture, individuals tend to respond more to social expectations or external influences. Therefore, their behaviors tend to be more aligned with group demands rather than personal attitudes. There is more flexibility between attitude and behavior. Furthermore, Gudykunst and Kacen proposed that individuals from Asian cultures tend to hide their negative emotions and only show their positive emotions to friends [13][14.] This explains why non-Asian subjects showed both negative and positive emotions whereas Asian subjects only reported their positive ones when participating in the interviews. In other words, the non-Asian subjects probably tended to report their true feelings while Asian subjects reported a compromise between their feelings and the researcher's expectations.

3.3.2 Emotion Reactions and Buying Intentions Versus Design Presentation Model

Purchasing a product involves a complex consideration of cost and benefits. There are also other factors that present in the decision making process. Hansen proposed both cognitive (perceived quality, price, developed attitude) and affective skills (emotional reactions.)” affect each other when consumers make decisions [1.] It is essential to evaluate a design by considering all of these perspectives, rather than simply asking a list of predetermined preference questions about a particular design.

Figure 8. Emotion Status and Buying Intentions Versus Design Presentation Model

Based on above findings, a model of design presentation regarding users' emotional feelings and buying actions was proposed (Figure 8.). This chart reveals the relations between the physical conditions (products and the environment) and the receiver's reactions (the participant's emotional reactions and buying intentions) during a design evaluation process. The physical condition includes the reality levels of a product and its surrounding environment. As shown in Figure 8, the receivers' involvement levels increase (shown as a bigger heart) when the level of realism in a product and environment representation move to the upper right corner. Being placed in an environment with stronger stimuli, people are more involved in the purchasing process; judging the product more critically and making careful decisions. In contrast, the receiver's involvement levels decrease (showed as a

smaller heart) when the level of realism move to the lower left corner. With weaker stimuli, people are less involved in the purchasing process, judge the product uncritically, and make decisions with less care.

Based on above research, the subjects' were willing to spend more money on the designs when they reported more positive emotions and stronger buying intentions. These influences are significant if the participant is more involved in the process. In other words, consumers would be more likely to make a purchasing action if they are highly involved in a purchasing process and feeling positively. As shown in Figure 8, the smiley face and the angry face demonstrate the total reactions of emotional reactions and buying intentions (the smiley face shows positive reactions; the angry face illustrates negative reactions). When a participant is highly involved in a physical condition (the bigger heart) and reports more positive feelings (smiley face) they are more likely to make a purchase (a bigger heart with smiley face on the upper right). In contrast, if a participant is less involved in a physical condition (the smaller heart), and also report positive feelings (angry face), they may not make a purchase.

Figure 9. Presentation Dissonance

The conflict between the reality levels of a product and its environment appear to negatively affect emotions. In the evaluation interview tool, two design models were built and presented in highly realistic virtual rooms. Then, the reality level of the designs was reduced to simplify further data analysis. For example, the color variations of the designs were limited to encourage attention on the main features of designs (appearance, lifting, and storage capability.) During the interviews, the subjects sensed the noticeable reality-conflict between the designs and the rooms; then, reported the uncomfortable feelings on the results of the emotional reactions (showed as the heart with angry face on Figure 9.) Similar to the idea of cognitive dissonance mentioned in the last section of this paper, the authors propose this situation as presentation dissonance – the perceived reality-conflict between a product and its environment. This explains why the subjects in previous research showed strong buying intentions regarding the designs, but didn't report corresponding positive emotions to them.

To avoid the negative effects of the presentation dissonance, the presentations of a design and its environment should match in levels of realism, as indicated by the diagonal line in Figure 9. For example, visualizing an idea in a sketched environment is a good way to clarify the idea in the pre-design stage; visualizing a concept in a colorized environment is an effective way to evaluate the concept in a mid-design stage; and displaying a real product in a showroom is an effective way to motivate a buying response in the post-design stage.

Eventually, this design presentation chart (Figure 9) gives a reference to examine both the ways designers communicate their designs and users react to designs during a design process. Utilizing the advantage of the upper right corner on Figure 9, customers in this condition are more willing to display real reactions, emotional feelings, and buying intentions. A distance away from the diagonal line on the left can result in negative feelings. Designers should consider or avoid this kind of presentation dissonance when conducting a design interview.

4. Conclusion

This study, developing a design evaluation method, clearly implies the connection between emotional reactions and buying intentions. Implementing this, or a similar method, can increase the chances a product will be successful in the marketplace.

Design evaluation responses should be analyzed based on not only the user's preferences for particular designs but also on the personal differences of the participants. During the design process, the designer should pay attention to individual's differences—ethnicity, culture, and personality, since they are highly related to user's emotional reactions, buying intentions and the appeal of a product. Both interactive interview media and presentation are necessary to better acquire responses. Presentation-dissonance, which may cause misunderstanding the user's response by negative emotions, should be recognized and avoided. We will continue to refine and evaluate this method with other researchers in the community. The goal is to better support the integration of research practices and theoretical outcomes in all aspects product design.

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